

EPEMC: Debunking Enki & Enlil as aliens... finally!

Primary Source text reveals the stellar origin of the myths pre-Babylon, pre-Bible, pre-Egyptian Dynasty

By Sf. Ramon Careaga, 2020

ENKI & THE WORLD ORDER

Ancient text, translated by scholars **not Sitchin**

Primary Source, and can be considered as a primary source, almost witness level

Short, brilliant, and straight-forward.

Answers questions about Potential identities of Nibru, and if Venus was indeed cometary.

Defines the relationship of the “two brothers” clearly.

Establishes Enlil’s identity firmly, and that of the Great Mountain.

Unvisited by Man

1-16 Grandiloquent lord of heaven and earth, self-reliant, father **Enki**, engendered by a bull, begotten by a wild bull, cherished by **Enlil** the Great Mountain, beloved by holy **An**, king, *mes* tree planted in the Abzu, rising over all lands; great dragon who stands in **Eridug**, whose shadow covers heaven and earth, a grove of vines extending over the Land, **Enki**, lord of plenty of the **Anuna** gods, **Nudimmud**, mighty one of the **E-kur**, strong one of heaven and earth! Your great house is founded in the Abzu, the great mooring-post of heaven and earth. **Enki**, from whom a single glance is enough to unsettle the heart of the mountains; wherever bison are born, where stags are born, where ibex are born, where wild goats are born, in meadows, in hollows in the heart of the hills, in green unvisited by man, you have fixed your gaze on the heart of the Land like a *halhal* reed.

Beloved by An (the dwarf star, aka Shamash, Kronos, etc.)

The Fertility God

Tree planted in the Abzu (so Abzu=Edin), the “Great mooring post of Heaven” - South Pole

THE Fertility God

So Zeus is a mistaken identity (as the Priest told Solon, the Greek forgot everything)

[17-31](#) Counting the days and putting the months in their houses, so as to complete the years and to submit the completed years to the assembly for a decision, taking decisions to regularise the days: father **Enki**, you are the king of the assembled people. You have only to open your mouth for everything to multiply and for plenty to be established.

[38-47](#) **Enlil**, the Great Mountain, has commissioned you to gladden the hearts of lords and rulers and wish them well. **Enki**, lord of prosperity, lord of wisdom, lord, the beloved of **An**, the ornament of **Eridug**, who establish commands and decisions, who well understands the decreeing of fates: you close up the days, and make the months enter their houses.

Enki cannot be a biological being

⁶¹⁻⁸⁰Enki, the king of the Abzu, justly praises himself in his majesty: "My father, the king of heaven and earth, made me famous in heaven and earth. **My elder brother, the king of all the lands,** gathered up all the divine powers and placed them in my hand. I brought the arts and crafts from the E-kur, the house of Enlil, to my Abzu in Eridug. **I am the good semen, begotten by a wild bull, I am the first born of An.** I am a great storm rising over the great earth, I am the great lord of the Land. I am the principal among all rulers, the father of all the foreign lands. I am the big brother of the gods, I bring prosperity to perfection. I am the seal-keeper of heaven and earth. I am the wisdom and understanding of all the foreign lands. With An the king, on An's dais, I oversee justice. With Enlil, looking out over the lands, I decree good destinies. He has placed in my hands **the decreeing of fates in the 'Place where the sun rises'.** I am cherished by Nintud. I am named with a good name by Ninhursaja. I am the leader of the Anuna gods. **I was born as the firstborn son of holy An."**

He is really, really Great

[86-88](#) In a state of high delight **Enki**, the king of the Abzu, again justly praises himself in his majesty: "I am the lord, I am one whose word is reliable, I am one who excels in everything.

[89-99](#) "At my command, sheepfolds have been built, cow-pens have been fenced off. When I approach heaven, a rain of abundance rains from heaven. **When I approach earth, there is a high carp-flood.** When I approach the green meadows, at my word stockpiles and stacks are accumulated. I have built my house, a shrine, in a pure place, and named it with a good name. **I have built my Abzu**, a shrine, in, and decreed a good fate for it. ...

[100-122](#) "The lords to me. I am **Enki!** **They stand before me, praising me.** The *abgal* priests and *abrig* officials who stand before me distant days. The *enkum* and *ninkum* officiants organise They purify the river for me, they the interior of the shrine for me. In my Abzu, sacred songs and **incantations resound for me.** My barge 'Crown', the 'Stag of the Abzu', transports me there most delightfully. It glides swiftly for me through the great marshes to wherever I have decided, it is obedient to me. ... **Nijir-sig**, the captain of my barge, holds **the golden sceptre for me.** I am **Enki!** He is in command of my boat 'Stag of the Abzu'. **I am the lord! I will travel! I am Enki!** I will go forth into my Land! I, **the lord who determines the fates**

Clearing up identities... Eridug=The Egg=The staircase=Step Pyramids/Zigurats

[1-133](#) He presented animals to those who have no city, to those who have no houses, to the Martu nomads.

[134-139](#) The **Anuna** gods address affectionately the great prince who has travelled in his Land: "**Lord who rides upon the great powers, the pure powers, who controls the great powers, the numberless powers**, foremost in all the breadth of heaven and earth; who received the supreme powers in **Eridug**, **the holy place**, the most esteemed place, **Enki**, lord of heaven and earth -- praise!"

[140-161](#) All the lords and rulers, the incantation-priests of **Eridug** and the linen-clad priests of **Sumer**, perform the purification rites of the Abzu for the great prince who has travelled in his land; for father **Enki** they stand guard in the holy place, the most esteemed place. They the chambers, they the emplacements, they purify the great shrine of the Abzu They bring there the tall juniper, the pure plant. They organise the holy in the great music room of **Enki**. **Skilfully they build the main staircase of Eridug** on the Good Quay. They prepare the sacred *uzga* shrine, where they utter endless prayers.

Neptune? first mentioned; the Tree = Cosmic Pole

[166-181](#) The lord, the great ruler of the Abzu issues instructions on board the 'Stag of the Abzu' -- the great emblem erected in the Abzu, providing protection, **its shade extending over the whole land** and refreshing the people, the principal foundation (?), the pole planted in the marsh, rising **high over all the foreign lands**. The noble captain of the lands, **the son of Enlil, holds in his hand the sacred punt-pole**, a *mes* tree ornamented in the Abzu which received the supreme powers in [Eridug](#), the holy place, the most esteemed place. **The hero proudly lifts his head towards the Abzu.**

6 lines missing or unclear

[182-187](#) **Sirsir**, the boatman of the barge, the boat for the lord. **Nijir-sig**, the captain of the barge, holds the holy sceptre for the lord. The fifty *lahama* deities of the subterranean waters speak affectionately to him. The stroke-callers, like **heavenly gamgam birds**

The complex role of the stellar breakup, these aren't people!!!

[188-191](#) The intrepid king, father **Enki** in the Land. Prosperity was made to burgeon in heaven and on earth for the great prince who travels in the Land. **Enki** decreed its fate:

[192-209](#) "**Sumer**, Great Mountain, land of heaven and earth, **trailing glory**, bestowing powers on the people from sunrise to sunset: **your powers are superior powers**, untouchable, and **your heart is complex and inscrutable**. Like heaven itself, **your good creative force (?)**, in which gods too can be born, is beyond reach. Giving birth to **kings who put on the good diadem**, giving birth to lords **who wear the crown on their heads** -- your lord, the honoured lord, sits with **An** the king on **An's dais**. Your king, the Great Mountain, **father Enlil**, the father of all the lands, has **blocked you impenetrably (?)** like a cedar tree. The **Anuna**, the great gods, have taken up dwellings in your midst, and consume their food in your *giguna* shrines with their single trees. Household **Sumer**, may your sheepfolds be built and your cattle multiply, may your *giguna* touch the skies. May your good temples reach up to heaven. **May the Anuna determine the destinies in your midst.**"

The wobbling Lord of plenty becomes the Lord of War

[210-211](#) Then he proceeded to the sanctuary of **Urim**. **Enki**, lord of the Abzu, decreed its fate:

[219-220](#) Then he proceeded to the land of **Meluha**. **Enki**, lord of the Abzu, decreed its fate:

[221-237](#) "Black land, may your trees be great trees, ...Heroes shall them on the battlefield as weapons!
May your bulls be great bulls, may they be bulls of the mountains! ... May all your silver be gold! May all
your copper be tin-bronze! ... May your men go forth like bulls against their fellow men!"

[238-247](#) He cleansed and purified the land of **Dilmun**. He placed **Ninsikila** in charge of it. He gave for the
fish spawn, ate its fish, bestowed palms on the cultivated land, ate its dates. **Elam** and **Marhaci**
..... to devour **The king endowed with strength by Enlil destroyed their houses, demolished**
(?) their walls. **He brought their silver and lapis-lazuli, their treasure, to Enlil, king of all the lands, in**
Nibru.

Plasma water flowed down when too near and low

[250-266](#) After he had turned his gaze from there, after father **Enki** had **lifted his eyes** across the **Euphrates**, he stood up full of lust like a rampant bull, lifted his penis, **ejaculated and filled the Tigris with flowing water**. He was like a wild cow mooing for its young in the wild grass, its scorpion-infested cow-pen. The **Tigris** at his side like a rampant bull. By lifting his penis, he brought a bridal gift. The **Tigris** rejoiced in its heart like a great wild bull, when it was born **It brought water, flowing water indeed: its wine will be sweet. It brought barley, mottled barley indeed: the people will eat it**. It filled the **E-kur**, the house of **Enlil**, with all sorts of things. **Enlil was delighted with Enki, and Nibru was glad**. The lord put on the diadem as a sign of lordship, he put on the good crown as a sign of kingship, touching the ground on his left side. Plenty came forth out of the earth for him.

Then Neptune/Poseidon, son of Kronos held sway

[267-273](#) **Enki**, the lord of the destinies, **Enki**, the king of the Abzu, placed in charge of all this him who holds a sceptre in his right hand, him who with glorious mouth submits to verification the devouring force of **Tigris** and **Euphrates**, while prosperity pours forth from the palace like oil -- **Enbilulu**, the inspector of waterways.

[274-277](#) He called the marshes and gave them the various species of carp, he spoke to the reedbeds and bestowed on them the old and new growths of reeds.

[278-284](#) He issued a challenge **Enki** placed in charge of all this him from whose net no fish escapes, him from whose trap no living thing escapes, him from whose bird-net no bird escapes,

Destruction is Nigh; Is Venus the origin of the Sahara Desert?

[285-298](#) The lord established a shrine, a holy shrine, **whose interior is elaborately constructed**. He established a **shrine in the sea**, a holy shrine, whose interior is elaborately constructed. The shrine, **whose interior is a tangled thread, is beyond understanding**. The shrine's emplacement is **situated by the constellation the Field**, the holy upper shrine's emplacement faces **towards the Chariot constellation**. Its **terrifying awesomeness is a rising wave**, its splendour is fearsome. The **Anuna** gods dare not approach it.

[299-308](#) He filled the **E-kur**, the house of **Enlil**, with goods of all sorts. **Enlil was delighted with Enki**, and **Nibru was glad**. **Enki** placed in charge of all this, over the wide extent of the sea, **her who sets sail in the holy shrine, who induces sexual intercourse**, who over the enormous **high flood of the subterranean waters, the terrifying waves, the inundation of the sea**, who comes forth from the, the mistress of **Sirara**

Terrifying BUT productive; who is Ickur?

[309-317](#) He **called to the rain of the heavens**. He as floating clouds. He made rising at the horizon. He **turned the mounds into fields** **Enki** placed in charge of all this him who rides on the great storms, **who attacks with lightning bolts**, the holy bar which **blocks the entrance to the interior of heaven**, the son of **An**, the **canal inspector** of heaven and earth -- **Ickur**, the bringer of plenty, the son of **An**.

[318-325](#) He organised ploughs, yokes and teams. The great prince **Enki** bestowed the horned oxen that follow, he opened up the holy furrows, and made the barley grow on the cultivated fields. **Enki** placed in charge of them the lord who wears the diadem, the ornament of the high plain, **him of the implements**, the farmer of **Enlil** -- **Enkimdu**, responsible for ditches and dykes.

The moon gods... (from Curse of Agade)

222-244 Again, Suen, Enki, Inana, Ninurta, Ickur, Utu, Nuska and Nisaba, all the gods whosoever, turned their attention to the city, and cursed Agade severely:

"City, you pounced on E-kur: it is as if you had pounced on Enlil! Agade, you pounced on E-kur: it is as if you had pounced on Enlil! May your holy walls, to their highest point, resound with mourning! **May your giguna be reduced to a pile of dust!**

Titan or Ganymede and maybe Callisto appear

[326-334](#) The lord called the cultivated fields, and bestowed on them mottled barley. **Enki** made chickpeas, lentils and grow. He heaped up into piles the early, mottled and *innuha* varieties of barley. **Enki** multiplied the stockpiles and stacks, and **with Enlil's help he enhanced the people's prosperity.** **Enki** placed in charge of all this **her whose head and body are dappled, whose face is covered in syrup, the mistress who causes sexual intercourse, the power of the Land, the life of the black-headed -- Acnan, the good bread of the whole world.**

[335-340](#) The great prince fixed a string to the hoe, and organised brick moulds. He penetrated the **like precious oil.** **Enki** placed in charge of them **him whose sharp-bladed hoe is a corpse-devouring snake that**, whose brick mould in place is a tidy stack of hulled grain for the ewes -- **Kulla**, who bricks in the Land.

Moons / Jupiter

Ganymede

Europa

Io

Callisto

You decide

Moon Titan Is More Compelling Than Mars ...
npr.org

Titan (moon) - Wikipedia
en.wikipedia.org

They could see/sense the electro-gravitic power

[341-348](#) He **tyed down the strings and coordinated them with the foundations**, and with the power of the assembly he planned a house and performed the purification rituals. The great prince put down the foundations, and laid the bricks. **Enki placed in charge of all this him whose foundations once laid do not sag**, whose good houses once built do not collapse (?), whose **vaults reach up into the heart of the heavens like a rainbow -- Mucdama, Enlil's master builder.**

[349-357](#) He **raised a holy crown over the upland plain**. He fastened a lapis-lazuli beard to the high plain, and made it wear a lapis-lazuli headdress. He made this good place perfect with grasses and herbs in abundance. He multiplied the animals of the high plain to an appropriate degree, he multiplied the ibex and wild goats of the pastures, and made them copulate. **Enki placed in charge of them the hero who is the crown of the high plain, who is the king of the countryside, the great lion of the high plain, the muscular, the hefty, the burly strength of Enlil -- Cakkan, the king of the hills.**

Order from Chaos; Jupiter steals some moons (forming retrogrades); Heracles appears! And he's losing water??

[368-380](#) He filled the **E-kur**, the house of **Enlil**, with possessions. **Enlil** was delighted with **Enki** and **Nibru** was glad. He demarcated borders and fixed boundaries. For the **Anuna** gods, **Enki** situated dwellings in cities and disposed agricultural land into fields. **Enki** placed in charge of the whole of heaven and earth the hero, the bull who comes out of the *hacur* forest bellowing truculently, the youth **Utu**, the bull standing triumphantly, audaciously, majestically, the father of the Great City (*an expression for the underworld*), the great herald in the east of holy **An**, the judge who searches out verdicts for the gods, with a lapis-lazuli beard, rising from the horizon into the holy heavens -- **Utu**, the son born by **Ningal**.

Venus is no moon! (Is she a space station? - joke)

[387-390](#) Then, alone lacking any functions, the great woman of heaven, **Inana**, lacking any functions -- **Inana** came in to see her father **Enki** in his house, weeping to him, and making her complaint to him:

[391-394](#) "**Enlil** left it in your hands to confirm the functions of the **Anuna**, the great gods. Why did you treat me, the woman, in an exceptional manner? I am holy **Inana** -- where are my functions?"

[422-423](#) "But why did you treat me, **the woman**, in an exceptional manner? I am holy **Inana** -- where are my functions?"

[424-436](#) **Enki** answered his daughter, holy **Inana** : "How have I disparaged you? Goddess, how have I disparaged you? How can I enhance you? ... I made you go forth I covered with a garment. I made you exchange its right side and its left side. ..."

Innana the first Karen?

The Woman?

No functions?

Clearly not speaking
biologically

The likely answer is
the functions refer to
orbital periods

[395-402](#)"Aruru, Enlil's sister, Nintud, the lady of giving birth, is to get the holy birth-bricks bowl of translucent lapis lazuli (*in which to place the afterbirth*). She is to carry off the hol

[403-405](#)"My illustrious sister, holy Nininsina, is to get the jewellery of *cuba* stones. She is t

[406-411](#)"My illustrious sister, holy Ninmug, is to get the golden chisel and the silver burin. when a king is born and the crowning with the crown when a lord is born are to be in her

[412-417](#)"My illustrious sister, holy Nisaba, is to get the measuring-reed. The lapis-lazuli me borders. She is to be the scribe of the Land. The planning of the gods' meals is to be in her

[418-421](#)"Nance, the august lady, who rests her feet on the holy pelican, is to be the fisheries her father Enlil.

Venus dominates the Ekur; Athena-goddess of War

[437-444](#)"Maiden **Inana**, how have I disparaged you? How can I enhance you? Amongst the ominous occurrences in the hurly-burly of battle, **I shall make you speak vivifying words**; and in its midst, although **you are not an *arabu* bird** (*a bird of ill omen*), I shall **make you speak ill-omened words** also. I **made you tangle straight threads**; maiden **Inana**, I made you straighten out tangled threads. I... I made **you colour tufted (?) cloth with coloured threads.**"

[445-450](#)"**Inana**, you heap up human heads like piles of dust, you sow heads like seed. **Inana**, you **destroy what should not be destroyed**; you **create what should not be created**. You remove the cover from the *cem* drum of lamentations, Maiden **Inana**, while shutting up the *tigi* and *adab* instruments in their homes. **You never grow weary with admirers looking at you**. Maiden **Inana**, you **know nothing of tying the ropes on deep wells.**"

[451-471](#)"But now, **the heart has overflowed**, the Land is restored; **Enlil's heart has overflowed**, the Land is restored. **In his overflowing heart of mankind,**"

